

Figure S2B – WT/WT individual

Exon 3-5
R 71 homozygous

Exon 6
G 230

Exon 6
CGT 232 wt=Arg (R)

Exon 7
CGG 293 wt=Arg (R)

Human Donor Sample

Exon 1-2

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 3-5

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 6 (Red is CGT/232=WT)

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 7a

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 7b

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Figure S2B – WT/HAQ individual

Exon 3-5
R71H het

Exon 6
CGT 232 wt=Arg (R),
G230A Het

Exon 7
CGG R293Q Het

Human Donor Sample

Exon 1-2

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 3-5

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 6

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 7a

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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Human Donor Sample

Exon 7b

Homo sapiens chromosome 5, GRCh38.p14 Primary Assembly

NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_000005.10

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